

Development of A Battery of *In Silico* Prediction Tools for Drug-Induced Liver Injury (DILI) from the Vantage Point of Translational Safety Assessment

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ABSTRACT

Drug induced liver injury (DILI) remains a challenge when translating knowledge from the pre-clinical stage to human use cases. Attempts to model human DILI directly based on information from drug labels have had some success; however, the approach falls short of providing insights or addressing uncertainty due to the difficulty of decoupling the idiosyncratic nature of human DILI outcomes. Our approach in this comparative analysis is to leverage existing pre-clinical and clinical data as well as information on metabolism to better translate mammalian to human DILI. The human DILI knowledgebase from U.S. FDA NCTR contains 1036 pharmaceuticals from diverse therapeutic categories. A human DILI training set of 305 oral marketed drugs was prepared and a binary classification scheme applied. The second knowledgebase consists of mammalian repeated dose toxicity with liver toxicity data from various regulatory sources. Within this knowledgebase, we identified 278 pharmaceuticals containing 198 marketed or withdrawn oral drugs with data from the U.S. FDA New Drug Application (NDA) and 98 active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) from ToxCast. From this collection, a set of 225 oral drugs was prepared as the mammalian hepatotoxicity training set with particular endpoints of pathology findings in the liver and bile duct. Both human and mammalian datasets were processed using various learning algorithms, including artificial intelligence approaches. The external validations for both models were comparable to the training statistics. These datasets were also used to extract species-differentiating chemotypes that differentiate DILI effects on humans from mammals. A systematic workflow was devised to predict human DILI and provide mechanistic insights. For a given query molecule, both human and mammalian models are run. If the predictions are discordant, both metabolites and parents are investigated for QSAR and species-differentiating chemotypes. Their results are combined using Dempster-Shafer Decision Theory to yield a final outcome prediction for human DILI with estimated uncertainty. Finally, these tools are implementable within an *in silico* platform for systematic evaluation. *The views presented in this article do not necessarily reflect the opinions of the US Food and Drug Administration or the National Institutes of Health. Any mention of commercial products is for clarification and is not intended as an endorsement.*

Graphical Abstract

For Table of Contents Only

ABBREVIATIONS

2D	Two-dimensional
3D	Three-dimensional
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AM1	Austin Model 1
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
API	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
CDER	Center for Drug Evaluation and Research
CSRML	Chemical Subgraph and Reaction Mark-Up Language
DILI	Drug-Induced Liver Injury
DST	Dempster-Schaefer Theory
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
FN	False Negative
FP	False Positive
GLP	Good Laboratory Practice
hDILI	Human Drug-Induced Liver Injury
HESS	Hazard Evaluation Support System Integrated Platform (from NITE Japan)
HOMO	Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital
InChI	IUPAC International Chemical Identifier
IOM	Inorganic/Organometallic/Metal
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry
k-NN	k-Nearest Neighbors
LR	Logistic Regression
LTKB	Liver Toxicity KnowledgeBase
LUMO	Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbital
MCC	Mathews Correlation Coefficient
METI	Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry
mHepTox	Mammalian Hepatotoxicity (as defined in the text)
MoA	Mode of Action
NAM	New Approach Methodology
NCTR	National Center for Toxicological Research

NDA	New Drug Application
NPV	Negative Predictive Value
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PLS	Partial Least Squares
PPV	Positive Predictive Value
QSAR	Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship
RF	Random Forest
ROA	Routes of administration
SAR	Structure Activity Relationship
SCCS	Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety
SD	Structure-data
SMILES	Simplified Molecular-Input Line-Entry System
SOT	Society of Toxicology
SVM	Support Vector Machines
TG-GATEs	Open Toxicogenomics Project-Genomics Assisted Toxicity Evaluation System
TN	True Negative
ToxRefDB	Toxicity Reference Database
TP	True Positive
U.S. EPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency
U.S. FDA	United States Food and Drug Administration
WOE	Weight of Evidence

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1. INTRODUCTION

Drug-induced liver injury (DILI) remains a major challenge in drug development, regulation, and safety assessment, especially when translating pre-clinical stage knowledge to human clinical studies or post-market safety concerns. Hepatotoxicity in general is one of the most important target organ toxicity endpoints of human health relevance. Understanding and reducing potential hepatotoxicity effects from active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) are still major hurdles, and predicting liver injury or failure due to drugs in real use cases is especially challenging. The ability to estimate DILI risks based on pre-clinical data is limited, and therefore many New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) are currently being actively pursued.¹

Adverse effects from DILI are often grouped by whether they are due to the intrinsic (dose-dependent) toxicity of the drugs or from idiosyncratic adverse reactions, suspected to result from adaptive immune responses.^{1,2} Whilst the idiosyncratic reactions are unpredictable, rare and not dose-dependent, most literature studies agree that DILI mainly depend on common underlying mechanistic paths involving reactive metabolites, mitochondrial toxicity, steatosis, cholestasis, transport, or innate immune activation.^{3,4,5} DILI findings, especially intrinsic DILI resulting from these mechanisms can be predicted in preclinical animal or in vitro studies. On the other hand, some drugs eliciting toxicities in humans via these mechanisms may not produce similar effects in pre-clinical studies, and so predicting potential DILI in humans based on pre-clinical results is not reliable in some cases. One of the many reasons for this shortcoming is believed to be differences in P450 metabolism as well as reactive metabolites across species, making knowledge of metabolism in both humans and pre-clinical animals an essential component.^{6,7}

Liver-related findings in toxicity databases are usually found in three areas: serum enzyme levels from clinical chemistry, organ weight, and pathology of the liver and bile duct. Pathologies reflecting hepatotoxicity are manifested by hepatitis, cholestasis (with and without inflammation), cholangitis, granulomatous hepatitis, steatosis (micro- and macro-vesicular), phospholipidosis, vascular lesions, and tumors. The categorization of liver injury involves a phenotypic change (e.g. cholestasis, steatosis, fibrosis, necrosis) that is a result of acute or chronic compound injury. Clinical and/or adverse reactions due to drug exposure range from serum enzyme elevations and jaundice to other severe symptoms requiring hospitalizations, hepatic failure leading to liver transplant, to other severe symptoms. Transforming controlled toxicity findings from pre-clinical studies to clinical observations and adverse

human reactions is difficult and efforts to predict hepatotoxicity have met with only limited success up to the present according to all the references cited in this study.

Unraveling these complex underlying relationships requires at minimum prediction systems for both human DILI and pre-clinical hepatotoxicity as well as metabolism data. A tool utilizing these data and analyses, to be presented here, will encompass a workflow applying predictions on humans and pre-clinical animals using both QSAR and rule-based knowledge, and then analyze the outcomes to distinguish species-metabolism dependency. Construction of a knowledgebase that can potentially provide such a translational perspective requires robust databases, prediction systems for human DILI and pre-clinical hepatotoxicity, and a hepatic metabolism database.

A human DILI dataset has been compiled at the U.S. FDA NCTR (National Center for Toxicology Research) based on FDA drug labels as part of the FDA projects on Liver Toxicity KnowledgeBase (LTKB).^{8, 9, 10, 11, 12} LTKB contains three components, DILI annotation, data collection, and model development. DILI Benchmark dataset, DILrank and DIList (DILI severity and toxicity) are parts of the DILI annotation effort.⁹ As the second component of this project, LTKB collected a broad range of data from both preclinical and clinical spaces some of which are made publicly available via LTKB including data for 287 drugs in the LTKB–Benchmark Dataset (LTKB-BD).¹³ The data were used to assess various hypotheses such as *in vitro* – *in vivo* extrapolation and the similarities between preclinical rat liver testing systems.^{14,15} For the third component, a variety of models were developed using DILI annotation from the *in silico*, *in vitro* and genomic data. Other than confidential business information and a few software features, most of the resources in LTKB are available publicly. The collaborative study presented in this paper is a part of this effort to leverage the data collected in LTKB and from the public domain. Other public database efforts include Open Toxicogenomics Project-Genomics Assisted Toxicity Evaluation System [TG-GATES]¹⁶ and DrugBank Database¹⁷. Based on these data- and knowledge-bases, a number of datasets have been published over a decade by Fourches,¹⁸ Zhu,¹⁹ Chen,^{8,9,10,11} Mulliner,²⁰ Luo,²¹ Kotsampasakou,²² Ai 2018,²³ and Thakkar.²⁴ These datasets serve as important resources used by numerous groups for hepatotoxicity modeling. especially for evaluating pharmaceuticals.

In particular, the 2016 compilation by Chen et al. assigned DILI annotations of 1036 drugs from LTKB to three verified categories (“No DILI”, “Less DILI”, “Most DILI”) and one category without verified causality (“Ambiguous”).^{11,25} In a 2020 publication, Thakkar et al.²⁴ expanded this dataset to 1279 drug substances based on LTKB criteria. This new dataset used binary classification of drugs by human hepatotoxicity and drug-induced liver injury severity and toxicity (DIList) such that the dataset can be

combined with other public datasets. To this end, we further updated DILLst dataset by adding curated chemical structures (SMILES and InChI) and registering them in the COSMOS Database²⁶. In the Venn diagram in Figure 1, the three most recent data sources for human DILI or hepatotoxicity data are compared; Kotsampasakou's dataset was excluded since the endpoint was limited to cholestasis.

Figure 1. Comparison of Three Human Drug Induced Liver Injury or Hepatotoxicity Datasets

The Mulliner set contains general chemicals as well as drugs, while the Ai and Thakkar's datasets are mostly drugs. Although these publications report the use of data from a handful of similar sources, there were many discrepancies in endpoint classifications across the sources. Data comparisons are made in the Supporting Materials.

Hepatotoxicity data from *in vivo* animal studies of non-pharmaceuticals are well represented in various public databases including HESS,²⁷ ToxRefDB,²⁸ RepDose,²⁹ and oRepeatTox/COSMOS databases.^{30,26} These sources often reflect regulatory evaluations from Japan (Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry, METI), the U.S. EPA and FDA, SCCS (Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety), and EFSA (European Food Safety Authority). On the other hand, large databases containing toxicity data for pharmaceuticals have been less available to the public. PharmaPendium,³¹ a commercial database from Elsevier, is available for study reports cited in the NDA documents at U.S. FDA Center for Drug Evaluation Research (CDER). It is critical to have access to the full scope of studies to determine whether a chemical (drug or API) is liver toxic and to transparently define the endpoint decision.

A wide array of *in silico* models to predict liver toxicity has been reported in the literature with training sets prepared from the sources mentioned above. Human DILI models based on FDA-approved drugs were published using random forest methods.³² This particular modeling strategy is one of several that will be employed in the battery approach presented in this work. The application of machine learning

methods was also reported by Kotsampasakou et al.²² on human cholestasis and by Mulliner et al.²⁰ on both human and pre-clinical data. Mulliner et al. divided the liver toxicity effects into two aggregated classifications, enzyme changes from clinical chemistry and morphology changes based on both hepatobiliary and hepatocellular endpoints.

For mechanism-based, rule-based predictions, excluding commercial sources, only a handful of open publications were available.^{33,34,35,36,37,38} However, active research projects are being pursued, e.g., by the Ontology consortium for developing a Hepatotoxicity Ontology and structural rules representing mechanistic or adverse outcome pathways.^{39,40}

The strategy described herein is to establish a pragmatic system that can give insights on the translatability from pre-clinical mammalian species to humans. The process is grounded on a set of predictive tools based on artificial intelligence (AI) approaches, mechanism-based structural rules, and metabolism data to interject the species differentiation. Only oral studies producing pathological changes were considered for pre-clinical data in order to simplify the construction of training sets. Clinical chemistry changes (enzymes, cholesterol, lipids) that are not correlated with the pathology changes at higher doses were not included in the endpoint decisions. The workflow is illustrated in Figure 2. For cases where the predictions between humans and pre-clinical mammals were discordant, the metabolites of the drug parents were either identified by search a metabolism database or generated in silico to obtain the final prediction outcome for human DILI potential.

Figure 2. Workflow within the Battery of Tools

Overall, the liver knowledgebase prediction system described in this study presents a practical and systematic workflow to assess how pre-clinical findings may be interpreted and to provide insights into the risks involved in human DILI. The liver toxicity prediction system was evaluated with an external dataset focusing on translational relationships varying across the space defined by chemical structures, therapeutic categories, and metabolism.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Liver Knowledgebase Data Sources

2.1.1 Human DILI Dataset for Pharmaceuticals

The DILIRank Dataset, published as part of the LTKB effort, was provided through collaboration by U.S. FDA NCTR.¹¹ The original dataset included 1036 drugs administered to humans via various routes (e.g., oral and intravenous, intramuscular or subcutaneous injections) and classified in terms of their DILI risk based on FDA drug labels after verification for causality. DILI descriptions covered serum enzyme elevations, occurrence of jaundice, hospitalizations, or other severe symptoms such as hepatic failure and/or liver transplant. The 2016 DILIRank Dataset provided a four-level categorization of drugs: “most”, “less”, “no” and “ambiguous” DILI concern. The dataset contained chemically diverse drugs including simple organics and inorganic/organometallic/metals (IOMs), protein sequences, polymers, and drug mixtures. There was a total of 72 non-structurable and 964 structurable chemicals, of which 873 organic drug structures were identified.

Figure 3 Preparation of Modellable Dataset from the FDA NCTR Knowledgebase

The dataset was further focused to 703 organic drugs with oral routes of administration (ROA). To prepare a modellable dataset, 166 drugs with an “ambiguous” DILI risk and 14 duplicates were removed, resulting in 523 oral drugs with unique, defined organic structures (Figure 3). Since the oral route dictates involvement of liver as the first-pass metabolism whereas injection routes (especially intravenous) follow mostly renal clearance bypassing hepatic metabolism, only data from oral studies were included whilst data from other routes of administration were reserved for interpreting species differences.

The final human DILI dataset for oral drugs has been modelled previously for 3-level (“most”, “less” and “no” DILI) ordinal models or 2-level (positive by combining “most” and “less” DILI and negative for “no” DILI) binary endpoints. The 2-level model was implemented in the ChemTunes•ToxGPS® chemoinformatics software platform⁴¹ based on the 523 drug dataset. To reduce possible data conflicts due to the “less” DILI classification, the QSAR training set of 305 oral drugs was identified using only the “most” and “no” DILI concerns and with no conflicts among any other data sources. *In silico* methods including structural rules and prediction models were developed based on this final dataset.

2.1.2 Pre-Clinical Mammalian Hepatotoxicity Dataset

Pre-Clinical DILI Dataset for Non-Pharmaceuticals Data for nearly 1800 compounds were compiled from various database sources well-known for reliable information (Table 1). These databases are available either in the public domain or via data exchange. A full scope of toxicity experiments spanning a variety of species and routes of exposure covering broad dose ranges are required to judge and compare the liver toxicity of a chemical. The databases were merged and the content was fused according to the study selection criteria described in previous publications [Yang 2017, Yang 2020].^{42,43} One inclusion criterion was the availability of full findings descriptions at the dose (treatment) level along with the complete description of study design parameters. In addition, inclusion of studies covering wide dose ranges was also considered important.

Table 1. Data Sources of Liver Knowledgebase

	ToxRefDB	RepDose	oRepeatTOX	HESS	ToxCast	Drugs@FDA (this study)
ToxRefDB	805	158	16	91	93	1
RepDose	ToxRefDB 2012: agrochemical, industrial, consumer product; RepDose 2010: industrial; RepDose and ToxRefDB have some common NTP data	533	30	139	0	1
oRepeatTOX	oRepeatTOX: Consumer Products, cosmetics, food chemicals (SCCS, EFSA, ECHA) Oral-only; ToxREFDB and oRepeatTOX have little overlap	RepDose and oRepeatTOX have quite different chemical space.	153	9	0	0
HESS	HESS: data from NEDO (New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization) and Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI)	HESS and RepDose have some overlap of chemical space.	HESS and oRepeatTOX have very little overlap	496	0	0
ToxCast	Over 120 pharmaceutical chemicals (93 QC'd) donated to ToxCast from Pfizer and GSK	No overlap of chemical space between RepDose and ToxCast APIs	No overlap of chemical space between oRepeatTox (cosmetics) and ToxCast APIs	No overlap of chemical space between HESS and ToxCast APIs	93	7
Drugs@FDA (this study)	Drug data from Drugs@FDA.gov site; 93 pharmaceuticals are included in ToxRefDB (TOxCast)	No overlap of chemical space between FDA Drugs and RepDose (other than 1 overlap)	No overlap of chemical space between FDA Drugs and oRepeatTox	No overlap of chemical space between FDA Drugs and HESS	Only 7 drugs are in common between FDA drugs (this study) and ToxCast	193

Study findings were described using an ontology approach. The findings were categorized by various assays, i.e., weight changes, food/water consumption, mortality, clinical signs, clinical chemistry, tissue chemistry, organ weights, pathology (macro and micro), and urinalysis. These assays yielded a variety of liver findings (e.g., liver enzyme, organ weight changes, fatty degeneration, pigmentation, vacuolization, inflammation, necrosis, etc.) specifying whether they were “treatment related”. The findings were further described by liver sites (e.g., acinus, various lobes and lobules, zone, parenchyma) and over four hundred pathology terms. These findings were then linked to diseases mapped into

categories such as cholestasis, steatosis/steatohepatitis, or fibrosis/cirrhosis and grouped to score the hepatotoxicity. The resulting knowledgebase contains 1457 records of industrial chemicals (~600), cosmetics and foods (~300), and agrochemicals (~500). After removing overlaps and resolving conflicts, we assigned 1100 unique structures with various hepatotoxicity classifications. Some of these data are available from the public COSMOS²⁶ and commercial ChemTunes databases.⁴⁴ Structural knowledge representing mitochondrial toxicity, cholestasis and steatosis mechanisms was then developed to classify and score the expressions based on the ontology-driven knowledgebase. Structural knowledge was coded in the Chemical Subgraph and Reaction Mark-Up Language (CSRML)⁴⁵ using the Chemotype Editor, and fragment-matching was performed in the ChemoTyper.⁴⁶ Fundamental procedures are described in the structural feature analysis in Section 2.2; however, in-depth details of the development of structural knowledge will be published separately.

Mammalian Hepatotoxicity Dataset of Pharmaceuticals

Pre-clinical pharmaceutical data were available from pharmacological reviews of the U.S. FDA New Drug Application (NDA) program [Drugs@FDA] for marketed drugs. The FDA NDA drug site was explored to build a pre-clinical dataset counterpart to the FDA NCTR's human DILI dataset of marketed drugs. When available, the pharmacological reviews from this site are comparable to the PharmaPendium database.³¹ The FDA reviewers' opinions and sponsors' conclusions were helpful in determining the final outcome of adverse hepatic pathology changes. Over 270 drug structures with repeated dose toxicity were compiled by expert-mode curation, from which 225 structures were prepared as the training set for pre-clinical QSAR models of pathology changes of liver and bile duct when treating with orally-administered drugs. The selection criteria of this drug set included 1) studies providing data on multiple species; 2) detailed dose-level toxicity data covering wide dose ranges preferably with PBPK and/or toxicokinetics profiles; 3) drugs with known human DILI data whenever possible. This compiled dataset will be referred to here as the mHepTox (mammalian hepatotoxicity) dataset. The Supporting Data contains the human DILList classification by Thakkar (1205) as well as the training sets for hDILI (305) and mHepTox (225) for pharmaceutical structures, with mappings to other public human liver datasets.

2.1.3 Drug Metabolism Data

ChemTunes BioPath Metabolism Database currently contains information on xenobiotics. The content mainly includes human hepatic metabolism mostly of drug and drug-like molecules for a total of 439 parents. These molecules are involved in 2,858 phase I and II reactions, resulting in 2,927 metabolites. The human *in vivo* and *in vitro* hepatocytes studies were harvested, curated and quality-controlled by

domain experts using primary literature, e.g., Drug Metabolism and Disposition⁴⁷ reference books,⁴⁸ and regulatory sources (NDA Pharmacological Review from Drugs@FDA).⁴⁹ On the study design level, information such as species, sex, strain, cell lines, route of exposure, organ/tissue, compartment, activation, microsome, cofactor, medium, duration, dosage and animal groups (if available) was additionally retrieved and stored. These biotransformations are captured on a molecular and atomic level that allows for their application in chemoinformatics context, e.g., to derive reaction rules validated by the database content to generate metabolites for new molecules for prioritization or profiling tasks.

ToxGPS LiverBioPath Metabolizer, a module within ChemTunes•ToxGPS®, was used to generate potential metabolites of drugs when experimental data were not available from the ChemTunes BioPath Metabolism database. The system is based on the similar methodology of expert knowledge and empirical scores developed by using a large metabolism database.⁵⁰ Putative human hepatic metabolites are generated by identification of labile sites in molecules that can undergo metabolic transformations. Within the LiverBioPath Metabolizer, over 140 metabolism rules covering both phase I (cleavage, hydrolysis, hydroxylation, lactam/lactone formation, oxidation, rearrangement, reduction) & Phase II (acylation, glucuronidation, glycation, methylation, phosphorylation, sulfation) reaction types are used to generate relevant transformation products. The rules are coded in CSRML⁴⁵ and have been validated against the LiverBioPath database, which also provides a likelihood measure for the reactions as well the identification of potential major metabolites.

2.2 Structural Features Analysis by Chemotypes

Chemicals were fragmented for in silico analysis using the public ChemoTyper application.⁴⁶ Both existing ToxPrints⁵¹ and newly designed features (using CSRML syntax) were searched for matches against the target datasets. The science of chemotypes and technological details of their implementation have been previously published.^{45, 52} The fingerprint files are converted to list the number of structures matched by each chemotype. Statistical analysis based on means and Z-scores is applied to identify chemotypes that differentiate negative (0) and positive (1) outcomes for the desired endpoint (e.g., pre-clinical hepatotoxicity or hDILI).⁴³

Structural rules were designed using the ToxPrint chemotypes as the building blocks. The new ChemoType Editor⁵³ software was employed when new chemotypes carrying mechanistic information were needed. Successive substructure searching within the ChemoTyper application allowed refinement of the fragments to develop new correlating structural rules. In most cases, ToxPrint chemotypes gave

sufficient differentiating power without additional modifications. Information regarding rules development will be published separately as part of the larger liver ontology project.⁵⁴

2.3 Battery of QSAR Models

2.3.1 Description of Modeling Process

Structure Processing. The data curation process provided SMILES representations of the chemical structures of interest. A unique IUPAC International Chemical Identifier (InChI) key was generated for each structure to identify structural duplicates, which were then manually reviewed to resolve potential structure conflicts in the primary step. Next, the CORINA Symphony⁵⁵ application was employed to identify and remove salt ions or unconnected small fragments in the original structures and to neutralize charged structures. Further, three-dimensional (3D) coordinates were generated for each structure. The two- and three-dimensional (2D and 3D) structure-data (SD) files were then used to calculate molecular descriptors. For structural alerts development, 2D tested forms were used, whereas 3D structures were used for QSAR models after resolving the conflicts due to the removal of small fragments or neutralization. These conflicts due to tested forms can also lead to toxicity study conflicts. At this secondary step of the conflict resolution, specific studies were reviewed and the more appropriate data were selected by expert mode.

Descriptors. Two general types of descriptors are used in QSAR modeling, physicochemical properties and structural “fingerprints”. The fingerprint for a molecule is a bit string denoting the presence or absence of specific structural fragments. The QSAR models developed here used fingerprints based on the ToxPrint chemotypes.⁵¹ ToxPrint fingerprints can be generated from the publicly available ChemoTyper⁴⁶ application or obtained for chemicals included in the EPA Computational Chemistry Dashboard.⁵⁶ Molecular properties were calculated from CORINA Symphony. Selected types of properties included “whole molecule” (BondsRot, HAccN, HAccO, HDonN, HDonO, Ro5ViolExt, Stereo, Weight, Complex, McGowan, TPSA, Polariz, Log S, XlogP), “shape” (Aspheric, Diameter, Eccentric, Rgyr, Span), and EMPIRE quantum mechanical (Hof:AM1, Homo:AM1, HomoLumoGap:AM1, Lumo:AM1) descriptors.⁵⁷

AI approach. In building the battery of QSAR tools, an approach including artificial intelligence (AI) was also pursued. There are many learning algorithms that can be used when building QSAR models, each with certain advantages and disadvantages, and it remains unlikely that any single approach will emerge as the “best” algorithm for all situations. For this reason, an ensemble approach was used here. For each

particular endpoint of interest (oral human DILI or oral mammalian hepatotoxicity), separate QSAR models were built using each of the learning algorithms described in the subsequent section.

Dimensional reduction. A reduced descriptor space was achieved by employing the partial least square (PLS) regression technique for the various learning algorithms. The number of ToxPrint chemotypes, molecular properties from CORINA Symphony, and PLS components were optimized during the modeling process.

Cross validation. A k -fold cross-validation scheme is employed to construct models which not only explain the training data sets sufficiently but are also capable of generalizing well to external observations for prediction. The k -fold cross-validation methodology involves splitting the training set compounds into k parts of equal size. Over a series of k iterations, each partition is withheld as a pseudo “test set” while the remaining $k-1$ partitions undergo the model training process. Once a model is trained, it is used to predict the members of the holdout partition. The process repeats until a prediction is made for all structures in the training set. The performance statistics calculated from cross-validation provide a reasonable estimate of the expected error on predictions for external datasets.

2.3.2 Description of Learning Algorithms

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). This is a diverse class of learning methods loosely inspired by the organization and interaction of neurons in the biological brain.⁵⁸ An ANN consists of a collection of interconnected units, called neurons or nodes, arranged into layers; the overall architecture of the ANN generally consists of an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. Descriptor data is fed directly into the input layer neurons and is subsequently transformed by the neurons of the hidden and output layers into predicted values on the endpoint of interest. Neurons manipulate data by transforming the weighed sum of the outputs of connected neurons from previous layers using transfer functions.^{59,60} The ANN is trained in a supervised manner by adjusting the weight assignments on each neuron through feed-forward and back-propagation algorithms. Training sample descriptor data is fed into the neural network which calculates a series of outputs given an initialized weighting scheme. These predicted outputs are compared to the actual response values for the samples, characterizing the network error. The effect of the neural weights on the error is then back propagated through the ANN in the reverse direction. Coupled with the gradient descent algorithm, successive iterations of feed-forward and back-propagation proceed until the neuron weights are found to minimize the error function.^{59,60} Much diversity is possible in ANN architecture; the number of neurons per layer, the number of hidden

layers, the transfer functions used for each node, and the connections between neurons may all be tailored to the application of interest.⁶¹

K-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN). This is a non-parametric regression or classification method in which the prediction on each test query is dependent upon the k closest training examples in the descriptor space. The proximity of a query to the compounds of the training set is determined using a distance metric, commonly the Euclidean distance, although other distance metrics may be used, depending on the nature of the variables. For classification tasks, the prediction of test instances is made by determining the most prevalent class among the k training samples; each training instance can contribute equally or the class totals can be weighted by a function of the distance between the query to the corresponding samples. Typically, the value of k and possible weighting functions are iteratively explored to determine the best parameter set for the final model under a cross-validation optimization strategy.^{62,63}

Logistic Regression (LR). This is a classical regression method, used here to fit a functional relationship between latent variables and the binary discrete response variables. The logistic function serves as an appropriate mapping between the descriptors and endpoint of interest. Probabilities associated with each possible class are also estimated.^{64, 65}

Random Forest Regression (RF). This is a tree-based ensemble method for generating predictions in classification and regression problems. A RF typically consists of many decision trees constructed using the recursive partitioning algorithm [Cutler 2012].⁶⁶ Each tree is initiated by a random sampling of training samples and, during tree construction, a random sample of descriptors are chosen at each non-terminal node to resolve splits. Once the “forest” of decision trees has been created, the prediction for a future test query is found by averaging the estimates of the response variable across all decision trees of the forest.⁶⁶ An optimized RF is determined by iterating over a number of tunable parameters in a cross-validated grid search: the number of trees in the forest, the number of features sampled for determining splits, and the stopping criteria defining terminal nodes.⁶⁶

Support Vector Machines (SVM). This non-parametric machine learning method is well-known for solving complex classification and regression tasks. Linear SVMs seek to orient a decision hyperplane in descriptor space such that members of opposing classes are partitioned by the hyperplane. Optimal orientations are computed by maximizing the distance between training samples of the different classes (called “support vectors”) and the hyperplane.^{67,68,69} Since it is often not possible to completely segregate class members in real-world problems, the algorithm includes tolerances for handling training samples on the wrong side of the hyperplane while still arriving at an optimized solution. Classification tasks

unsuitable for linear treatment in the original descriptor space may still be explained in a linear fashion following transformation to a higher or infinite-dimensional kernel space. Such problems remain computationally possible through employment of kernel functions and the “kernel-trick”. Though computationally intractable for very large datasets, SVM methods are versatile, can be used for both linear and nonlinear modeling, often out-perform other algorithms, and are well-documented in the literature.^{67,68,69}

2.3.3 Decision Theory for Weight of Evidence (WOE) Outcome

A decision theory approach based on Dempster-Shafer Decision theory (DST) was used to combine multiple sources of evidence (e.g., predictions from QSAR models and structural rules) and to estimate the uncertainty associated with each predicted outcome.⁷⁰ A key feature of DST is that the reliability of each source is rigorously taken into account; for example, a WOE result obtained by combining the prediction from an ensemble of QSAR models with predictions from a structural rule gives more weight to the more accurate approach, as determined from validating the performance of each against a known test set.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Species-Differentiating Structural Features

Since drugs interact with specific macromolecule targets, it is useful to group drug activities and potential toxicities into structural classes. In drug discovery programs, these structure activity relationships (SARs) have been one of the most fruitful areas of computational approaches. Rules development for target organ toxicities is also a well-established area. For example, the liver steatosis pathways proposed by Luckert et al.⁷¹ based on the concept of Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) can be associated with structural rules. Applying similar approaches to cholestasis, mitochondrial toxicity, and reactive metabolites, a set of structural rules are implemented in ChemTunes•ToxGPS®. Although the structural rules development process is not presented in detail here, this section will demonstrate how structural features differentiate between human DILI and mammalian hepatotoxicity.

In pre-clinical studies, it is well-known that chemicals show different sensitivity toward the test animals used. For example, lovastatin showed no indication of liver histopathology in subchronic or chronic rat studies in pre-clinical GLP studies, whereas the liver was the target organ for mouse. Entacapone gave no pathology findings in rat and mouse, while dog and monkey were extremely

sensitive. For some drugs such as azelastine hydrochloride, study results for rabbits were considered more closely related to human findings. From this perspective, it is understandable that human DILI would also be difficult to understand based solely on the pre-clinical studies of various species. Possible reasons for these observations may be differences in metabolism as well as immune responses. Metabolic differentiation between species may be explored from the structural rule-base perspective.

3.1.1 Chemotypes Differentiating Humans and Mammals

In Figure 4, a comparison of structural feature correlations between the human drug induced liver injury (hDILI) and mammalian hepatotoxicity (mHepTox) datasets is illustrated. The features include mostly ToxPrint chemotypes used as fingerprints, but also the structural rules developed based on the underlying hepatotoxicity mechanisms. The length of a bar in Figure 4 indicates the frequency of the class (depicted in log scale). The longer the bar, the more structures populate the class. Each bar is colored based on the Z-scores obtained by treating the binary categorical values (e.g., negative or positive) of the endpoint from both the human DILI rank or preclinical hepatotoxicity as numeric values 0 and 1 for this calculation. The Z-score of a chemotype class was calculated by:

$$z_c = (\bar{y}_c - \bar{y}) / \sqrt{(n_0 / n_c)(S^2 / N)}$$

where n_0 is the number of structures not containing the chemotype, n_c is the number of structures containing the chemotype, N is the total number structures in the set ($n_0 + n_c$), S is the standard deviation of the whole set, \bar{y} is the mean of the whole set and \bar{y}_c is the mean of the subset containing a chemotype class. The mean of each class is listed in Figure 4. The color coding of each bar according to the Z-scores in Figure 4, includes: dark orange for $z_c \geq 2$, light orange for $1 \leq z_c < 2$, gray for $-1 < z_c < 1$, light blue for $-1 \geq z_c > -2$, and dark blue for $z_c \leq -2$. Thus, if a chemotype class has a highly positive correlation with either human DILI or mammalian hepatotoxicity, the class is colored orange; if a class has a highly negative correlation with the endpoints, the class is colored blue.

Four scenarios of special interest in Figure 4 are chemotypes that are: 1) positively associated with hDILI and mHepTox; 2) negatively associated with both endpoints; 3) positive in hDILI but negative in mHepTox; and 4) negative in hDILI but positive in mHepTox. These latter discordant features were used as building blocks to define structural rules for differentiating human results from those for the combined mammalian group. Although the mammalian data can technically be investigated for each species, it was deemed impractical to build models specific to only one species to compare species-specific pre-clinical results. The common problem of insufficient data for single species can be overcome

by pooling data as done here to form the mammalian dataset. Although there are many other reasons why attempting to build many species-specific models would be problematic, these are beyond the scope of this paper. Table 2 lists a set of selected chemotypes to compare the endpoints for the two datasets. Chemotype names appearing in bold font indicate that the feature appears in both the human and mammalian datasets. If the chemotype feature showed significant correlation in both datasets with the same trend (either negative or positive), then the names are depicted in bold and black font. If the chemotype indicated human positive and mammalian negative correlations, then the feature names are underlined and colored purple. Likewise, for human negative and mammalian positive-correlated chemotypes, feature names are in italics and colored cyan.

Table 2. Comparison of Structural Features in Human vs. Mammalian Liver Toxicity

	Human DILI	Mammalian HepTox
POSITIVE FEATURES*	halide_aromatic-X , <u>amine_aromatic</u> carboxylicAcid_aromatic, <u>carboxylicAcid</u> <u>aliphatic</u> , ketone_aromatic, carboxamide, carbonyl_ab-unsaturated , ether_aromatic, nitro_aromatic, <u>sulfonyl</u> , <u>sulfonamide</u> furan, thiophene, thiazole, <u>imidazole</u> . triazole , piperazine, pyrimidine, <u>pyridine</u> . diazine (1,3-), azepine , aromaticAlkene_Ph- C2_acyclic_generic (stilbenoid), <u>path 5 bidentate propandiamine (NCCCN)</u>	halide_aliphatic-X, halide_aromatic-X , carbonyl_ab-unsaturated , <u>alcohol_diol_(1,3-)</u> , ketone_aromatic, <u>ketone_aliphatic</u> , nitrile, carbamate, triazole , pyran, pyrazole, azepine, <u>steroid_generic_[5_6_6_6]</u> , <u>aromaticAlkane_Ar-C-Ar</u> , <u>alkaneBranch_neopentyl_C5</u> , path_5_bidentate_propandiamine (NCCCN), <u>path_4_OCC(OH)CN</u>
NEGATIVE FEATURES*	amine_aliphatic, carboxylicEster_aliphatic , aliphatic alcohol, <u>alcohol_diol_(1,3-)</u> , alcohol_diol_(1_2-), <u>ketone_aliphatic</u> , carboxamide, quatN_generic, pyrrole, piperidine , <u>steroid_generic_[5_6_6_6]</u> , <u>aromaticAlkane_Ar-C-Ar</u> , aromatic_alkaneBranch_propionic, <u>alkaneBranch_neopentyl_C5</u> , alkaneCyclic_C6 , <u>path_4_OCC(OH)CN</u>	<u>amine_aromatic</u> <u>carboxylicAcid</u> <u>aliphatic</u> , carboxylicEster_aliphatic , <u>sulfonyl</u> , <u>sulfonamide</u> quatN_generic, <u>imidazole</u> <u>pyridine</u> pyrrole, diazepine_(1_4-)

*A full list of ToxPrint features, shortened names, and statistics is available in the Supporting Information. Shortened ToxPrint names are used for simplicity.

To summarize, some chemotypes, e.g., aromaticAlkene_Ph-C2_acyclic (stilbenoid), triazole, or sulfonamide in Tamoxifen, Fluconazole, or Sildenafil exhibited statistically significant and similar correlations in both humans and mammals. Other chemotypes are associated positively with mammalian hepatotoxicity, but negatively with human DILI. These include steroid_generic_[5_6_6_6],

alcohol_diol_(1,3-), ketone_aliphatic, aromaticAlkane_Ar-C-Ar, alkaneBranch_neopentyl_C5, and path_4_OCC(OH)CN in Budesonide or Pindolol.

Figure 4. Selected ToxPrint Chemotypes Differentiation of Human vs. Mammalian In Vivo Studies
 Bars are colored according to Z-scores: $z_c \geq 2$ (dark orange), $1 \leq z_c < 2$ (light orange), $-1 < z_c < 1$ (gray), $-1 \geq z_c > -2$ (light blue), and $z_c \leq -2$ (dark blue). A full list of ToxPrint features, shortened names, and statistics is available in the Supporting Information (2). Shortened ToxPrint names are used for simplicity.

3.1.2. Case Examples of Differentiating Chemotypes

In this study, we use Zolmitriptan and Celecoxib as examples to further illustrate the analysis. Zolmitriptan is a member of the triptan class of 5-hydroxytryptamine(5-HT)_{1B/1D/(1F)} receptor agonists. Celecoxib is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug believed to be involved in the inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis, primarily via inhibition of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2). Table 3 illustrates the use of the ToxPrint chemotypes to compare the structural correlation with the endpoints, human DILI and mammalian hepatotoxicity.

Celecoxib was originally labelled as “less DILI concern” and classified as positive in the binary scheme for human DILI. In pre-clinical GLP studies, this drug did not result in pathological findings in the liver or bile duct. Celecoxib contains sulfonamide, pyrazole, and aromaticAlkane_Ph-C1 (toluyl) chemotypes. Sulfonamide exhibits a strongly positive association with human DILI, but a negative association with mammalian hepatotoxicity. Likewise, the pyrazole group is neutral in human DILI while positive for mammals. The aromaticAlkane_Ph-C1 (toluyl) chemotype is neutral in human DILI, but negative in mammals. These observations are largely consistent with the fact that celecoxib is human DILI positive but mammalian hepatotoxicity negative.

Table 3. Comparison of Features and Endpoints for Two Drugs (Celecoxib and Zolmitriptan)

	Human DILI	Mammalian Hepatotoxicity
Celecoxib	Positive aromaticAlkane_Ph-C1_acyclic (toluyl) sulfonamide pyrazole	

Zolmitriptan, on the other hand, is not reported to be hDILI positive (“no DILI concern”) whereas foci of hepatocellular necrosis and leucocyte necrosis are found in rat livers. The indole, oxazole, carbamate, and amine_ter-N_aliphatic chemotypes matched the structure. The carbamate group is positively associated in both mammals and humans. Indole was positive in mammals, but negative in humans while aliphatic amine is neutral in mammals but negative in humans. Oxazole was neutral in both humans and mammals. From the chemotype matching profile depicted in Table 3, we can see that Zolmitriptan would be positive for mammalian hepatotoxicity due to net positive contributions while having no human DILI concern due to net negative contributions from various chemotypes. Using the positive probability of these chemotypes, it is possible to calculate the overall conditional probability to estimate whether a structure would be positive or negative. Although a more formal treatment of this approach will be published elsewhere, this observation gives insight into the predictions of liver toxicity using a QSAR approach.

3.2 QSAR Models for Human Drug Induced Liver Injury

3.2.1. QSAR Model Results for Human DILI (hDILI) for Oral Drugs

For QSAR models on human DILI from oral drugs, the endpoint was defined by the binary classes of most-DILI and no-DILI concerns following the removal of drugs with “ambiguous” and “less-DILI” concerns. Drugs with the “most-DILI concern” classification are hence classified due to DILI-related withdrawal, labels with boxed warnings, or warnings and precautions with severe DILI indications, such as jaundice with hospitalization, hepatic failure, liver transplant, and death. Drugs of “less-DILI concern” have warnings and precautions for mild DILI indications or adverse reactions in the drug labels. The final QSAR training set consisted of 166 positives (“most-DILI concern”) and 139 negatives (“no-DILI concern”).

Table 4 summarizes the performance of the QSAR models based on the 305 drug training set for predicting human DILI for oral drugs. As shown in the table, all individual models yielded quite similar

performance. Whilst the training set is slightly skewed toward positives (55% most-DILI), all five learning algorithms seem to handle the imbalance quite well. The SVM, ANN, and k-NN models were further selected as the best overall performers when combining to obtain an ensemble prediction. When “less-DILI” drugs were included as part of the positives (results not shown for this 523 drug training set), all models show similar performance in sensitivity-related parameters; however, the specificity decreased by 16% (decrease of NPV and Matthews correlation coefficient by 15% and 13%, respectively). Although the 2-class model decreased the training set size (by removing “less DILI concern”), the clear distinction between “most-DILI” and “no-DILI” was helpful.

The influential ToxPrint chemotypes and properties from various models were analyzed to understand the correlation to the endpoint. A few examples of chemotypes positively influencing liver injury for humans with the highest loading are amine_aromatic, hetero_[5]_Z_1_3-Z (5-membered heterocyclic ring with 1,3 positions of heteroatoms), carboxylicAcid_aromatic, and halide_aromatic-X_generic. On the contrary, amine_alicyclic, amine_aliphatic, piperidine, pteridine, or benzyl alcohols tend to be influential for negative predictions. It is important to point out that these ToxPrint chemotypes influencing QSAR models are consistent with those identified based on the structure-feature correlation (using Z-scores) with the endpoint. The most influential molecular properties included HOMO/LUMO Gap (AM1), HOMO (AM1), water solubility (LogS), number of hydrogen bond acceptors, molecular weight, complexity, XlogP (octanol-water partition coefficient), and the largest principal moment of inertia. The energetics from quantum descriptors describe chemical reactivity aspects whereas the shape descriptors such as moment of inertia can be important in receptor bindings.

3.2.2. External Validation of hDILI Model

The external validation dataset largely contained the most recent data published from the FDA (Thakkar 2020). The 350 structures with binary classifications, which were not included in the 2016 dataset received from the FDA, were used as the initial basis. In addition, records with conflicting calls in other human liver injury datasets (Ai and Mulliner compilations) were removed from the validation set since there were 5-30% discrepancies between different sources. The resulting set was further filtered to include only oral route of administration to maintain a consistent comparison throughout the study. The final external validation set consists of a total of 65 drugs with 29 positives (DILI) and 36 negatives (Non-DILI).

1 Table 4. Summary of Model Performance Statistics¹ for Human DILI for Oral Drugs

	Methods used	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	MCC	Balanced Accuracy	TP	FP	TN	FN
Combining Method	Majority Rule ² ANN, SVM, KNN	0.820	0.861	0.769	0.823	0.825	0.639	0.815	143	32	107	23
Dimension Reduction	Learning Method ³	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	MCC	Balanced Accuracy	TP	FP	TN	FN
	PLS SVM	0.800	0.801	0.798	0.833	0.773	0.603	0.800	133	28	111	33
	PLS ANN	0.797	0.831	0.754	0.812	0.798	0.597	0.792	138	34	105	28
	PLS KNN	0.797	0.855	0.726	0.791	0.810	0.591	0.791	142	38	101	24
	PLS Logistic	0.780	0.813	0.740	0.796	0.773	0.561	0.777	135	36	103	31
	PLS RF	0.777	0.819	0.726	0.784	0.780	0.554	0.772	136	38	101	30

2 ¹Model Performance Statistics:

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, \text{ Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}, \text{ PPV} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}, \text{ NPV} = \frac{TN}{TN + FN},$$

3 Accuracy (concordance) = $\frac{TP + TN}{N}$, Balanced accuracy = average of sensitivity & specificity,

$$\text{MCC (Matthews correlation coefficients)} = \frac{TP \times TN - FP \times FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}}$$

4 ²Majority rule is applied to the results such that the majority of the outcomes determines the final decision for prediction of each structure

5 ³Modeling details: The number of chemotypes in the various models was 65 (SVM), 194 (ANN), 200 (KNN), 270 (Logistic), and 220 (RF); the
6 number of properties used was 22 (SVM), 9 (ANN), 28 (KNN), 7 (Logistic), and 20 (RF). ANN used 1 hidden layer with 21 neurons; the Logistic
7 regression regularization parameter was 0.1; SVM used a regularization parameter of 4.3 and the radial basis function kernel. KNN used 9
8 neighbors. RF used 25 or fewer leaf nodes and a maximum depth of 12.

9

10 These structures were run through the battery of models and the aggregated results (based on
11 the Majority Rules) are given in Table 5. The same external validation set was also run through the models
12 prepared from the 523 drugs, which treated the “less DILI concern” as positives. As expected, the external
13 validation resulted in lower specificity (54 %) whereas the sensitivity was much better (90%). This
14 validation study based on the model using the 305 training set (i.e., “most” and “no” DILI concern) was
15 considered acceptable to move onto the next step.

16 Table 5. External Validation of Human DILI Models for Oral Drugs

External Validation Set	Concordance (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Balanced Accuracy (%)	TP	FP	TN	FN
65 drugs (29 POS & 36 NEG)	74.6	82.8	63.9	73.3	24	13	23	5

17 3.3 Mammalian Hepatotoxicity of Drugs

18 3.3.1 Mammalian Pathology (mHepTox) Model for Oral Drugs

19 As described previously in section 2.1.2, a training set of 225 3D structures with adverse pathology
20 findings in liver and bile duct was used for QSAR modelling of mammalian hepatotoxicity. It is important
21 to note that this is not a general hepatotoxicity model, but a companion model to explore the human DILI
22 due to oral drugs in this study. We included only the drugs for which a wide variety of species studies
23 were available, preferably regulatory GLP studies. Therefore, this dataset includes results from studies in
24 at least a majority of the following species: rat, mouse, dog, primates (monkey, marmoset). In addition,
25 studies reporting changes in enzyme and lipid levels only found in clinical chemistry without
26 corresponding pathological changes in the liver and bile duct were not considered in this model. This
27 particular training set contained 139 positives (62%) and 86 negatives (38%), the slight skew towards
28 positives being a result of our attempt to identify pre-clinical data for well-known human DILI drugs. 51 of
29 the structures in this dataset also had human study data available; the study endpoint results were
30 concordant for 42 of these and discordant for 9. For example, Budesonide, Betaine, and Pindolol were
31 labelled with “no-DILI concern”, but as “hepatotoxic” in the mammalian set.

32 The same modeling approach was employed as in the hDILI modelling and results are tabulated
33 in Table 6. Although a stratified sampling approach was attempted to obtain more balance between
34 positives and negatives, simply using all data outperformed this technique.

35

Table 6. Summary of Model Performance Statistics for Mammalian Hepatotoxicity for Oral Drugs

Combining Method	Methods used	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	MCC	Balanced Accuracy	TP	FP	TN	FN
Majority Prediction ¹	SVM, RF, LR, KNN	0.706	0.705	0.707	0.811	0.597	0.410	0.706	98	25	61	41
Dimension Reduction	Learning Method ²	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	MCC	Balanced Accuracy	TP	FP	TN	FN
PLS	SVM	0.725	0.748	0.689	0.804	0.638	0.439	0.719	100	28	58	39
PLS	ANN	0.721	0.777	0.632	0.783	0.642	0.416	0.705	108	33	53	31
PLS	KNN	0.727	0.779	0.644	0.787	0.658	0.432	0.711	109	33	53	30
PLS	Logistic	0.716	0.717	0.716	0.813	0.609	0.428	0.717	99	26	60	40
PLS	RF	0.725	0.758	0.672	0.795	0.643	0.434	0.715	100	28	58	39

36 ¹See footnote "1" in Table 4.

37 ²Modeling details: The number of chemotypes in the various models was 245 (SVM), 180 (ANN), 249 (KNN), 227 (Logistic), and 245
38 (RF); the number of properties used was 11 (SVM), 17 (ANN), 5 (KNN), 13 (Logistic), and 11 (RF). ANN used 2 hidden layers with 10
39 neurons in each; the Logistic regression regularization parameter was 0.009; SVM used a regularization parameter of 5.5 and the
40 radial basis function kernel. KNN used 7 neighbors. RF used 6 or fewer leaf nodes.

41

42 The most strongly influential structural features and molecular properties in these models are examined
 43 and compared with those of the hDILI models. The ToxPrint chemotypes positively influencing mHepTox
 44 model predictions include aromaticAlkane_Ph-C2, aminoAcid_alanine, carboxylicEster_acyclic,
 45 carboxylicEster_alkyl, alkaneBranch_neopentyl_C5, X[any]_halide, pyridine, benzimidazole, amine_sec-
 46 NH_aromatic, indane, ethylenOxide_EO1(O), path_4_bidentate_aminoacetaldehyde, and amine_sec-
 47 NH_generic. Chemotypes that are negatively influencing the mHepTox model predictions include
 48 alcohol_sec-alkyl, hetero_[7]_generic_1-Z, azepine, pyran. alcohol_sec-alkyl, ketone, and
 49 path_5_bidentate_propandiamine (NCCCN). These chemotypes are quite different from those identified
 50 as influential in the hDILI model. The most influential properties included the number of hydrogen bond
 51 donors and acceptors, number of Lipinski rule-of-5 violations, HOMO:AM1, HOMO/LUMO Gap:AM1,
 52 diameter, asphericity, span, and radius of gyration. It is worth noting that the quantum energetics and
 53 shape descriptors turned out to be important for both hDILI and mHepTox endpoints. Again, as seen
 54 previously with hDILI model, chemical reactivity and receptor bindings are captured by quantum
 55 energetics and shape descriptors, respectively.

56 **3.3.2. External Validation of Mammalian Pathology Model**

57 In principle, the same set of drugs used to validate the hDILI models can be included for the
 58 mHepTox validation dataset. The reality was that many of these drugs did not have sufficiently detailed
 59 public data required to judge mHepTox as described in Section 2.1.2, hence the external set size was
 60 reduced to 41 drugs for which we have information from Drugs@FDA. This difficulty is especially true for
 61 drugs with negative outcomes. Under the same data criteria and GLP compliance protocols, we must
 62 check several species (rat, mouse, dog, monkey) to ensure that these negatives can be true for both
 63 training and external validation sets. In addition, as in the external validation of the hDILI model for oral
 64 drugs, 21 equivocal predictions were removed from the external validation results. The results are
 65 summarized in Table 7.

66 Table 7. External Validation of Mammalian Hepatotoxicity Models for Oral Drugs

External Validation Set	Concordance (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Balanced Accuracy (%)	TP	FP	TN	FN
41 drugs (21 POS & 20 NEG)	64.3	71.4	60.0	65.7	15	9	12	5

67 Having taken precautions to ensure high quality and reliability of external drug sets, these two models
 68 were used to compare the human and mammalian knowledge space.

69 3.4 Weight of Evidence Evaluation Workflow

70 3.4.1 Concordant Predictions Between Humans and Mammals

71 As depicted in Figure 3, our *in silico* process for predicting human DILI uses models for both
72 humans and mammals to strengthen the reliability of the outcome. In a case where predictions from
73 humans and mammals are concordant, either positive or negative, the outcomes for the human DILI
74 potential will be given higher confidence and priority.

75 3.4.2 Discordant Predictions Between Humans and Mammals

76 Prediction Case A: Human DILI Negative / Mammalian Hepatotoxicity Positive

77 In cases where the human and mammalian predictions are not concordant, the human predictions
78 would be evaluated again after consideration of QSAR, structural rules, and metabolism. This evaluation
79 will use the WOE combination method based on Dempster-Shafer Decision Theory.⁷⁰ For example,
80 applying the various QSAR models to Zolmitriptan, we obtain a probability of 0.34 for human DILI-concern
81 (negative) and 0.62 for mammalian hepatotoxicity (positive). In this case, the predictions are confirmed by
82 the experimental data; however, for purposes of illustration, we will proceed as if such experimental data
83 were not available to confirm the prediction and so we would have to rely on the *in silico* workflow
84 proposed in this study. In this case, we apply QSAR and structural rules to both parents and metabolites
85 in our evaluation, which are then combined according to the decision theory rules.

86 Zolmitriptan is extensively metabolized via CYP 1A2 into a number of components including the
87 three main metabolites observed *in vivo*: M2: N-desmethyl-zolmitriptan, M3: zolmitriptan N-oxide, and
88 M6: indole acetic acid derivative. In the case of Zolmitriptan, humans have higher M2 and M6 plasma
89 exposure levels compared to M2 and M3 levels observed in mice. Figure 5 depicts the structures of the
90 three metabolites.^{72,73}

91

92 M2: N-desmethyl-zolmitriptan M3: zolmitriptan N-oxide M6: indole acetic acid-zolmitriptan

93

Figure 5. Major metabolites of zolmitriptan *in vivo*

94 Combining all the evidence (Table 8) using the weight of evidence approach requires individual
 95 probabilities (likelihood of occurrence) and reliabilities of each evidence source (e.g., goodness of fit).

96 **Table 8 Combination of Evidence for Zolmitriptan Human DILI Potential**

Structure	Evidence sources combined	prob(POS) lower bound	prob(POS) upper bound	uncertainty	DST probability bar†
Parent	QSAR: hDILI Rule: amine_aliphatic Rule: indole	0.094	0.34	0.246	
Metabolite M2	QSAR: hDILI Rule: amine_aliphatic Rule: indole	0.07	0.274	0.204	
Metabolite M3	QSAR: hDILI Rule:bond:amine_aliphatic Rule: indole Rule: nitro_C*	0.079	0.299	0.22	
Metabolite M6	QSAR: hDILI Rule: amine_aliphatic Rule: indole Rule: carboxylicAcid_aliphatic	0.375	0.786	0.411	
Combination Outcome		0.026	0.279	0.253	

97 *As the nitro-metabolite is not as important in human as it is in mouse, this rule was not included in the
 98 combination outcome.

99 †The probability bar is color coded to indicate the bounds on each probability associated with each predicted
 100 outcome. The length of the green bar represents the probability to be negative, red to be positive, and yellow the
 101 uncertainty. When neither red or green bars is greater than 0.50, the prediction is equivocal.

102 A combination outcome was calculated by combining each of *in silico* predictions (QSAR and structural
 103 rules) for each species (parent and metabolite). Also considered was the percentages of each test
 104 substance found in the plasma when applying the decision theory rule. The final probability of
 105 Zolmitriptan to be human DILI-positive (prob(POS)) was computed to fall between 2.6% (lower bound)
 106 and 27.9% (upper bound) with an uncertainty of 25.3 %. Therefore, this prediction informs us that
 107 zolmitriptan would most likely be negative although uncertainty if relatively high.

108 **Prediction Case B: Human DILI Positive / Mammalian Hepatotoxicity Negative**

109 Celecoxib is extensively metabolized by a single metabolic pathway in all species (via CYP2C9,
 110 CYP3A, and CYP 2C19, CYP2B, CYP3A, CYP2D15) including humans. In humans, CYP2C9 dominates. The
 111 methyl group of Celecoxib is first oxidized to a hydroxymethyl metabolite, followed by additional oxidation

112 of the hydroxymethyl group (M1) to a carboxylic acid (M2) metabolite. Structures of the metabolites are
 113 depicted in Figure 6.

114
 115 **Figure 6. Major metabolites of Celecoxib in Vivo**

116 Following the same process described in the previous case, Table 9 summarizes the additional evidence
 117 we consider, namely QSAR results and species-differentiating structural features for both parent and
 118 metabolites. For Celecoxib, a very clear case of human DILI potential can be concluded from the
 119 combination outcome. The probability of being positive was estimated at 95.1 to 99.9 % with an
 120 uncertainty of 4.8%.

121 **Table 9 Combination of Evidence for Celecoxib Human DILI Potential**

Structure	Evidence sources combined	prob(POS) lower bound	prob(POS) upper bound	uncertainty	DST probability bar
Parent	QSAR: hDILI Rule: sulfonamide	0.928	0.988	0.060	
Metabolite M1	QSAR: hDILI Rule: sulfonamide Rule: alcohol_aliphatic	0.580	0.916	0.336	
Metabolite M2	QSAR: hDILI Rule: sulfonamide Rule: carboxylicAcid_aromatic	0.972	0.999	0.027	
Combination Outcome		0.951	0.999	0.048	

122 As demonstrated in these two examples (Tables 8 and 9), although the hDILI prediction of the
 123 parent was in conflict with the mammalian model, consideration of both QSAR and alerts for both parent
 124 and metabolites confirmed the correct human DILI potentials.

125 **3. CONCLUSIONS**

126 This study approaches the problem of predicting human drug-induced liver injury by establishing
127 reliable databases for both human and mammals, followed by applying species-differentiating structural
128 features, QSAR models for humans and mammals, and metabolism knowledge. The human DILI datasets
129 and interpretation of data were provided through collaboration from FDA NCTR. Pre-clinical toxicity
130 studies of approved drugs were compiled from the pharmacological reviews available from Drugs@FDA
131 site. Based on these databases, species-differentiating chemotypes are developed to help identify
132 chemical effects of these structural features on human and mammals and whether a chemotype is
133 correlated preferentially to human or mammals. Training and external validation datasets for QSAR
134 models were established from these databases. Metabolism data were obtained from the database
135 whenever possible and human in vitro metabolites were generated when needed. A pragmatic workflow
136 was developed for predicting human DILI based on all the components described above. When prediction
137 results based on species-differentiating chemotypes and QSAR models are concordant for human and
138 mammals, then this prediction is the expected outcome. When the predictions from the above step are
139 discordant between human and mammals, additional steps are taken to apply metabolism knowledge and
140 evaluate the variety of metabolites for species-differentiating chemotypes and QSAR models. To increase
141 the confidence of the final prediction outcome for human DILI, a weight of evidence method based on
142 Dempster-Shafer Decision Theory was applied to combine DILI potentials for the parents and metabolites.
143 This workflow is logical, transparent and actionable for implementation as a robust in silico prediction
144 tool.

145 **4. SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

146 Supplementary data related to this article are provided as an Excel file (Supporting
147 Information_Tables1-5.xlsx.) and can be downloaded from the journal site.

148 (1) Training sets used in this paper

149 Training sets compiled for the development of hDILI (oral human DILI) and mHepTox (oral mammalian
150 hepatotoxicity) QSAR models are listed.

151 (2) ToxPrint statistics in this paper

152 The full set of ToxPrint chemotypes describing the two training sets (hDILI and mHepTox) are listed
153 along with the statistical evaluation results including number of hits, % positives, % negatives, mean,
154 and Z-core for each chemotype. This table also provides mapping of short chemotype names (used in
155 the article for simplicity) to the formal titles of the ToxPrint chemotypes.

156 (3) DILIST dataset (Thakkar 2020) chemistry update

157 The chemistry section of the DILIst dataset from Thakkar 2020 was updated. The compiled chemistry
158 information includes SMILES, InChI and InChI Key notations for the structures of the tested chemicals.
159 The chemical information is also registered in the COSMOS Database and the test chemical InChI keys
160 were mapped to CMS-IDs.

161 (4) Human DILI datasets: comparison of public datasets

162 Comparisons across the various public dataset for chemistry information and human DILI
163 classifications were analysed. The datasets included Mulliner, Ai and Thakkar, as well as current hDILI
164 training set in this article.

165 (5) Mammalian Liver Toxicity datasets: comparison of public datasets

166 Comparisons across the various public dataset for chemistry information and mammalian
167 hepatotoxicity classifications were analysed. The datasets included Mulliner and the mHepTox
168 training set in this article.

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